

Impact of E-Learning on Higher Education: A Study of Himachal Pradesh University

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Abstract:

Electronic media is very useful sources for the development of learning process in higher education. It is digital 21st century cannot be achieve high results in learning and educational process without integrating new information and communication technologies in the education system. The development of higher education is connected with the comprehensive modernization in all areas of learning, research and innovations, and improving the coordination, flexibility and adaptation to the needs of society. Present paper focuses on efficiency of using sources of E Learning media i.e. E Magazines, E Books, E Journals and E newspapers among the students of Himachal Pradesh University. In this paper attempts has been made to analyze the impact of E learning on the development of higher education in the university. The paper also highlights the key role of Himachal Pradesh University for improvement and development of the educational process supported by modern technology; for facilitating e-learning to help students develop and enrich

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their learning skills in IT environment.

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Introduction

The use of enormous integrated set of computer and internet tools and resources in the new learning environments allows us to achieve more efficient and effective training. The students are no longer passive consumers of the educational programs and services, but active participants in the educational process. Their skills and competencies to work effectively with digital technologies are prerequisite for successful and responsible solving and presentation of scientific problems and case studies.

The modernization of education suggests that the students not only have to acquire skills and habits to work with the growing volume and more sophisticated information streams but have to possess ability to get new knowledge, independently to build the overall cognitive process in the surrounding IT environment. In the new IT environment of special importance is the human adaptation to ever-changing conditions of working and life that require development of a number of key competencies associated with effective and efficient use of IC technologies. In this regard, the students' training gets a new dimension. Through the use of digital technology in the learning process the students acquire skills to identify different sources of information in applications such as electronic media or video, to communicate through newsgroups, online discussion forums, web blogs or chat rooms, to search databases of local and global networks and create their own sites. It is suggested that the students also understand how to support the information society's creative potential and innovation, how to understand problems of legality and reliability of the information. Work in the information society requires a critical and reflexive attitude towards available information and responsible use of the interactive media.

Review of literature

Aixia and Wang (2011) found that the vast majority of students who were satisfied with an e learning environment held positive beliefs and attitudes towards it; perceived satisfaction was identified as one of four factors that helped explain 83.8% of the variance of student attitude. **Al-adwan and Smedley (2012)** has been explores the factors that influenced the development of learning through technology at two Jordanian universities, focusing on full-

time staff and students. The research investigated the technological factors that could influence the involvement of both groups in participating. It also explored their attitudes and readiness to integrate learning through technology into their learning experiences. Outcomes demonstrated that students in Jordan need to increase the level of their technological skills to significantly benefit from the opportunities offered by e-learning. Considerable preparatory support is required to ensure that faculty and students feel adequately and appropriately supported in their individual learning processes. Further studies could be undertaken to explore the strategic and operational opportunities focusing on technological readiness, skills and attitudes alongside cultural influences before e learning can have a significant impact to influence changing practices within the Jordanian student learning experience. **Bhuasiri, Xaymoungkhoun, Zo, Rho and Ciganek (2012)** found that in developing countries the most significant factors were related to increasing technology awareness and improving attitude towards e-learning, enhancing basic technology knowledge and skills, improving learning content, requiring computer training, motivating users to utilize e learning systems, and requiring a high level of support from the university. **Rahamat et al. (2012) Wu Tennyson & Hsia (2010)** Positive learning climate and performance expectations affect student satisfaction, and performance expectations provide the greatest contribution to learning satisfaction. Users (students and instructors) will hold positive attitudes towards e-learning if they recognize that it would help them improve their learning and teaching effectiveness and efficiency. **Chen and Huang (2012)** stated that understanding student attitudes can help expand e learning system functions and meet student needs, which should further increase the impact of learning and enhance satisfaction with the learning process. **Kumar and Bajpai (2015)** revealed that the E-learning has been revealed in this study a positive impact on achievement motivation and academic performance contrary to the expectations of this study. The study also found that the concluded that in order to improve motivational effectiveness and academic achievement, higher education should consider aiming to develop e-learning strategies that encourage greater engagement and also take into consideration the different learning styles found within the student body.

Need of the study

The present study is based e learning on higher education. The Himachal Pradesh University is a state university and student enrolled from different district, state and also from tribal area of the state. Present paper focuses on efficiency of using sources of E Learning media i.e. E Magazines, E Books, E Journals and E newspapers among the students. The main objective of the study is to examine the impact of e learning on higher education among the students. The 21 century is era of highly engaged with information technology and use most of the time social sites. The whole of the developing countries adopted the information technology in every sector. The education sector is most important on the basis of information technology. The present paper attempts has been made that how to use effectively information technology for the purpose of education sector.

Objectives

- To study the students opinions regarding e media and e learning habits.
- To analyze the impact of e learning on higher education.

Research Methodology

The study was carried out to see the Impact of e learning on higher education: A Study of Himachal Pradesh University. The study was based on primary as well as secondary data. The Primary data was collected from the students and research scholars through questionnaires and personal interviews. Secondary data was collected from internet websites, Magazines, newspapers and annual reports. The sample size was taken 120 and convenience sampling was used for data collection. Mean, standard deviation, skewness and chi square test have been used for the analysis of data.

Data analysis and results

Table: 1. Opinions of students regarding use of different e learning sources

Elearning Sources	S.D	D	N	A	S.A	Total	Mean	S.D.	Rank	Chi	P value
Google	-	-	-	42	78	120	4.65	.489	1	10.8	P<.01
Yahoo	-	-	24	65	31	120	4.05	.677	2	24.05	P<.01

Wikipedia	4	8	44	26	38	120	3.71	1.086	3	52.33	P<.01
Youtube	14	10	16	38	42	120	3.70	1.33	4	36.66	P<.01
Facebook	6	20	50	44	-	120	3.10	.85	5	42.4	P<.01
Twitter	12	50	50	8	-	120	2.45	.76	9	53.6	P<.01
Microsoft network	4	32	48	30	6	120	3.01	.92	6	58.33	P<.01
Rediff	8	38	42	32	-	120	2.81	.90	7	23.2	P<.01
Money control	20	48	18	22	12	120	2.65	1.24	8	32.33	P<.01

Source: Field survey, August, 2018

It is noted that mean score is revealed more than the average standard score (3), and rank is provided according to the highest mean value is ranked first and lowest mean score ranked lowest as the mean value is noted i.e. Google (4.65), Yahoo (4.05), Wikipedia (3.71), YouTube (3.70), Facebook (3.10) and MSN (3.01) and hence ranked 1 to 6 which inclined that majority of respondents scattered toward higher side on five-point rating scaled. It concludes that these search engine and social websites which is playing very vital information for development of higher education among the students of the university.

Furthermore, chi square test revealed significant about these source of E learning at 1 percent level of significance. It concludes that there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents.

However, it has been also revealed the mean score less than average slandered score (3), and rank is provided according to the highest mean value is ranked first and lowest mean score ranked lowest as the mean value is noted i.e. Rediff (2.81), Money control (2.65) and twitter (2.45) and hence ranked 7 to 9. Further, it has been inclined that the majority of respondents scattered toward lower side on five-point rating scale. It is concluding that these websites provide less information for development of higher education among the students of the university. Furthermore, chi square test revealed significant about these source of E learning at 1 percent level of significance. It concludes that there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents.

Figure 1: Ranking for opinions of student regarding search engine and social sites

Most using e media sources for e learning:

It is clear from table that mean score is revealed more than the average standard score (3), and rank is provided according to the highest mean value is ranked first and lowest mean score ranked lowest as the mean value is noted i.e. E- Dictionary (3.35), E- newspaper (3.5), E lectures (3.25) and E- journals (3.23) and hence ranked 1 to 4 which inclined that majority of respondents scattered toward higher side on five-point rating scaled. It concludes that these search electronic media which is playing very vital information for development of higher education among the students of the university. Furthermore, chi square test revealed significant about these source of electronic media at 1 percent level of significance. It concludes that there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents.

Table 2: Habits of E Media for E learning (most efficiently, efficiently, Fairly, Rarely and very rarely)

Source of E- learning	VR	R	F	E	ME	Total	Mean	SD	Rank	chi	P value
E -Magazines	12	42	40	22	4	120	2.7	.99	5	47.0	P<.01
E -Journal	-	26	50	34	10	120	3.23	.88	4	27.7	P<.01
E -news paper	4	18	36	38	24	120	3.5	1.07	1	32.3	P<.01
E -Books	18	42	38	18	4	120	2.56	1.02	6	41.3	P<.01
E -Dictionaries	8	16	42	34	20	120	3.35	1.11	2	31.67	P<.01
E- lecture	14	18	28	44	16	120	3.25	1.21	3	25.67	P<.01
Inflibnet	86	34	-	-	-	120	1.28	.45	7	22.5	P<.01

Source: Field survey, August, 2018

Figure 2: Ranking habits of respondents for e media

However, it has been also revealed the mean score is less than average slandered score (3), and rank is provided according to the highest mean value is ranked first and lowest mean score ranked lowest as the mean value is noted i.e. E- magazine (2.75), E- books (2.56) and Inflibnet and hence ranked 4 to 7. Further, it has been inclined that the majority of respondents scattered toward lower side on five-point rating scale. It is concludes that these websites provides less information for development of higher education among the students

of the university. Furthermore, chi square test revealed significant about these source of E learning at 1 percent level of significance. It concludes that there is significant difference in the opinion of the respondents.

Impact of e learning on students:

Table 3 Depicts that in statement First 89.17 percent respondents believe that e learning is effective for development of higher education and 10.83 percent respondents is not believe in e learning is effective for development of higher education In statement second 65 percent respondents believe that adequate sources are available in the university regarding e learning for students and 35 percent respondents believe that minimum sources are available in the university regarding e learning for students. In statement third 76.67 percent respondents believe that students are self-motivated for e learning in the university and 23.33 percent respondents are not self-motivated for e learning in the university.

Table 3: Impact of E- learning on student:

Sr. No.	Statements	Yes	No
1.	Do you think that e learning is effective for development of higher education?	107 (89.17)	13 (10.83)
2.	Do you think that adequate sources are available in the university regarding e learning for students?	78 (65)	42 (35)
3.	Do you think that students are self-motivated for e learning in the university?	92 (76.67)	28 (23.33)
4.	Do you think that books and other study material easily available for study?	75 (62.50)	45 (37.50)
5.	Do you think that e learning is cheaper than books?	67 (55.84)	53 (44.16)

Source: Field survey, August, 2018

In statement fourth 62.50 percent respondents believe that books and other study material are easily available for study and 37.50 percent respondents believe that books and other

study material are not easily available for study. In statement fifth 55.84 percent respondents believe that e learning is cheaper than books and 44.16 percent respondents believe that e learning is not cheaper than books.

Conclusion

The 21st century is era of highly engaged with information technology and use most of the time social sites. The whole of the developing countries adopted the information technology in every sector. The education sector is most important on the basis of information technology. The study reveals that the more than average user of e media uses the Google, yahoo and Microsoft net search engine and YouTube, Facebook and Wikipedia also. The majority of respondents scattered toward higher side on five-point rating scaled and revealed that these search engine and social websites which is playing very vital information for development of higher education among the students of the university.

However, on the basis of habits of e learning found that the majority of respondents using more than average E newspapers, E journals, E dictionaries and online lecture. Further, it has been conclude from the above study the students and research scholars using mostly e media in higher education and found significant difference in the opinions of respondents toward habits of e media for e learning.

The impact of e learning found that the e media playing a vital role in the development of higher education and e learning is effective for the development of higher education. The university provides adequate sources for e learning like e media internet facility in most of the departments and some of department also provides Wi-Fi facilities. Further, the study shows students and research scholars self-motivated for e learning.

Finally, the study revealed that maximum respondents in favorable condition, they think that e learning is effective for development of higher education and students are self-motivated for e learning in the university. They also think that books and other study material are easily available for study and e learning is cheaper than books.

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